

http://plugin04.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

```

4 <head>
5 <meta charset="UTF-8">
6 <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, i
7 <link rel="profile" href="https://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9 <title>Marketing Digital Tools | Agência de Marketing
10 <!-- The SEO Framework by Sybre Waaijer -->
11 <meta name="robots" content="max-snippet:-1,max-image-preview:
12 <meta name="description" content="Marketing Digital Tools | Ag
13 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
14 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
15 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
16 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
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18 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
19 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
20 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingdi
21 <meta property="og:locale" content="pt_PT" />
22 <meta property="og:type" content="website" />
23 <meta property="og:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools | A
24 <meta property="og:description" content="Marketing Digital Toc
25 <meta property="og:url" content="http://plugin04.marketingdigi
26 <meta property="og:site_name" content="MARKeting Digital Tools
27 <meta name="twitter:card" content="summary_large_image" />
28 <meta name="twitter:site" content="@mktdigitaltools" />
29 <meta name="twitter:creator" content="@fogebandido" />
30 <meta name="twitter:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools |
31 <meta name="twitter:description" content="Marketing Digital To
32 <meta name="twitter:image" content="http://plugin04.marketingc
33 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin04.marketingdigitalto
34 <script type="application/ld+json">{"@context":"https://schema
35 <script type="application/ld+json">{"@context":"https://schema
36 <meta name="google-site-verification" content="sQBJ98u1EC3V5-f
37 <!-- / The SEO Framework by Sybre Waaijer | 5.02ms meta | 1.26
38 <link rel='dns-prefetch' href='//s.w.org' />
39 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
40 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
41 <script type="text/javascript">
42 window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl":"https://\//s.
43 !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("ca
44 </script>
45 <style type="text/css">
46 img.wp-smiley,
47 img.emoji {
48 display: inline !important;
49 border: none !important;
50 box-shadow: none !important;
51 height: 1em !important;
52 width: 1em !important;
53 margin: 0 .07em !important;
54 vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
55 background: none !important;
56 padding: 0 !important;
57 }
58 </style>
59 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wp-block-library-css' href='ht
60 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wc-block-style-css' href='http://g
61 <link rel='stylesheet' id='dashicons-css' href='http://plugi
62 <link rel='stylesheet' id='everest-forms-general-css' href='h
63 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-layout-css' href='http
64 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-smallscreen-css' href=
65 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-general-css' href='htt
66 <style id='woocommerce-inline-inline-css' type='text/css'>
67 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
68 </style>
69 <link rel='stylesheet' id='font-awesome-css' href='http://plu
70 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-style-css' href='http://plug
71 <style id='zakra-style-inline-css' type='text/css'>

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Detetad Organization

0 ERROS (1)0 AVISOS 2 ITENS

Organization	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
@type					Organization
WebSite url					http://plugin04.marketingdigitaltools.com/
name					Marketing Digital Tools
logo					http://plugin04.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/cropped-Logo-MDT-ICON-RS-1.png
sameAs					https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/
sameAs					https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools
sameAs					https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools/
sameAs					https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFiw/featured
sameAs					https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/